

Paleo Plant Foods: An Examination of Carbohydrate Consumption in Late Pleistocene Hominins

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Abstract

This paper aims to reconstruct the diets of late Pleistocene hominins, focusing on the existing evidence of carbohydrate consumption. It will proceed by analyzing dental calculus and archaeological studies, which will shed light on how late Pleistocene hominins consumed and processed carbohydrates. This paper will show that some populations of late Pleistocene hominins consumed carbohydrates derived from various plant sources and processed these sources through grinding and cooking. These findings illuminate the substantial divergence in the consumption patterns of late Pleistocene hominin and modern human carbohydrate consumption, particularly in the fiber content that accompanied carbohydrate consumption. This will enhance our understanding of the divergence between the diets of our late Pleistocene ancestors and modern populations today, highlighting an important reality that could have modern day health implications.

Introduction

Dietary reconstruction is a significant undertaking, particularly with regard to populations that lived in the late Pleistocene era. The existing data is often fragmented and incomplete. Populations of hominins that lived during this period consumed resources that were available in their environment, indicating that the diets among these populations varied greatly across geographical region and time period. Therefore, this paper cannot aim to reconstruct a comprehensive dietary reconstruction for all hominins that lived in the late Pleistocene era. This paper only aims to reconstruct a partial picture of consumption, focusing on evidence of carbohydrate consumption and processing.

Modern scientific tools can provide some evidence regarding late Pleistocene hominin consumption patterns. This paper will detail such evidence, focusing on plant consumption and processing. This analysis will be structured into several sections.

First, the paper will outline the scientific and technical methodology for reconstructing the diets of late Pleistocene hominins. It will highlight the methods that scientists use to infer dietary consumption, the methods that are particularly valuable for reconstructing plant consumption, and the limitations of such methods.

Then, this paper will examine the evidence of carbohydrate consumption among late Pleistocene hominins. This will outline archaeological findings and dental calculus analysis that provide direct evidence of carbohydrate consumption. The findings illustrate

some important insights into what carbohydrate consumption looked like among some late Pleistocene hominin populations, allowing the extrapolation of some broader trends that characterize their plant diets.

This section will also highlight the existing archaeological and anthropological evidence regarding the extra-somatic processing of plant foods by late Pleistocene hominin populations. This evidence consists of stone tools used for grinding and pounding plants, as well as plants exhibiting evidence of thermal processing.

Then, the paper will transition from outlining the hard evidence to analyzing the presented evidence. It will offer insights and analysis that result from the archaeological evidence. This section will present the insight that carbohydrates played an important role in the diets of some populations of late Pleistocene hominins. Crucially, it will offer insights into how the landscape of carbohydrate consumption significantly differs from the carbohydrate consumption patterns of modern humans, particularly in the fiber content that accompanies carbohydrate consumption.

This paper will conclude by highlighting the main contributions of this paper, and the implications of the findings.

Methodology for Reconstructing Diet

In order to analyze the consumption patterns of late Pleistocene hominins, it is crucial to understand how

such reconstruction is scientifically feasible. While this is a challenging task, given the limited and fragmented evidence, scientists can utilize various methodologies to infer the presence of certain dietary components. This section will outline such methods, highlighting their strengths and weaknesses in inferring plant consumption.

Scientific Tools for Reconstructing Diet

Three primary methods are used to analyze the dietary components of ancient hominin populations. These methods are dental calculus analysis, dental micro wear analysis, and isotopic analysis [1], [2].

Dental Calculus: Analyzing dental calculus refers to the technique of analyzing material trapped in hardened dental plaque, primarily consisting of calcium phosphate [3]. Archaeological dental remains can contain trapped food micro particles, allowing scientists to infer materials consumed during an individual's life. This method is particularly valuable in reconstructing plant diets, as it provides direct evidence of specific plant consumption [4], [5].

Dental Microwear Analysis: Dental microwear analysis refers to the technique of analyzing wear patterns and surface damage present on dental remains [6]. While this method is valuable in constructing long term dietary consumption, it lacks the ability to provide specific data on plant consumption. This method can provide only a general snapshot on the categories or physical properties of dietary plants [2]. Thus, this method lacks the granularity of data that this paper requires, as it does not provide *specific*, identifiable information on plant consumption.

Isotope Analysis: Isotope analysis refers to the technique of analyzing bone collagen for the presence of carbon and nitrogen isotopes [7]. These isotopes become integrated in an individual's bones throughout their life, allowing scientist to measure the accumulation of these isotopes and reconstruct dietary patterns. However, isotope analysis is also significantly constrained with regard to inferring plant consumption. This technique primarily provides a long term snapshot of an individual's sources of dietary protein, limiting its ability to extrapolate *specific* plant and carbohydrate consumption [7].

Using Dental Calculus to Infer Plant Consumption

Based on the analysis of various scientific methodologies for reconstructing diet, this paper will primarily focus on dental calculus analysis. The granularity of data required to reconstruct specific patterns of car-

bohydrate consumption indicates that dental calculus is most suitable.

Dental calculus contains micro fossils that, when extracted and analyzed, can provide direct evidence of dietary consumption [4], [5], [8], [2]. This is particularly valuable for analyzing the various plant sources that late Pleistocene hominin consumed [5], [8]. Researchers can determine not only the presence of plant foods, but they can pinpoint the taxa of the plant from which the micro particles originated [4], [5].

Figure 1 displays a physical context in which micro particles remains are preserved. The image displays several dental remains, with blue arrows pointing to the areas on the teeth where hardened plaque entraps dietary particles.

Figure 1: Deposition of dental calculus on Fuyan Cave hominins teeth. Modified from [9]

Dental calculus is analyzed by first decalcifying the samples using hydrochloric acid (HCl) [4]. This releases entrapped materials within the dental calculus, which are further analyzed and identified. Once isolated, the microparticles are viewed under a microscope and morphologically compared to modern day proxies. This allows for the identification of a diverse array of materials, including microcharcoal, pollen grains, fungal spores, phytoliths, insect fragments, fibers, and, crucially, starch granules [4], [5].

Starch granules have significant morphological

variations, allowing scientists to pinpoint the taxa from which the granules originate [4], [5]. This provides the basis for reconstructing the plant diets of late Pleistocene hominins. By identifying not only the presence of starch granules, but also the taxa from which the granule originated, this paper can piece together a landscape of plant consumption among some late Pleistocene hominins.

While morphological examination is commonly used as the standard for microparticle identification, other emerging techniques provide an even stronger basis for identification. DNA analysis and thermal desorption and pyrolysis gas chromatography mass spectrometry (TD-GC-MS and Py-GC-MS) yield even more definitive conclusions in identifying plant materials [4], [10].

Limitations of Dental Calculus

While dental calculus offers important and valuable insights into reconstructing the plant diets of late Pleistocene hominins, the technique is not without its drawbacks. One of the most significant limitations is the minuscule proportion of starch grains that actually get embedded in an individual's dental calculus. The sheer quantity of granules consumed over an individual's lifetime, compared to the handful of starches that get entrapped in the dental calculus indicates that this analysis is limited [4]. Specifically, dental calculus analysis can indicate the presence of a dietary element, but it cannot be used to reconstruct a complete record of dietary intake.

Furthermore, processes such as cooking, chewing, and natural diagenesis can degrade the structure of the starch granules. While this can often enrich findings, by providing evidence of dietary processing through thermal or non-thermal means, the structural breakdown that occurs provides additional uncertainty in identifying microparticles [4], [5].

Given these factors, it is important to contextualize findings from dental calculus. While these findings offer important insights into reconstructing diets, they cannot provide a complete, comprehensive landscape of dietary consumption. Recent studies have aimed to test the accuracy of these results by examining dental calculus on a population with known diets.

A study on a living population in Japan, the Tve population, set out to evaluate the accuracy of dental calculus. It found that while plant microparticles entrapped in dental calculus may not provide insights into the individuals consumption patterns, they can provide insights into the populations consumption patterns, an interesting result [2].

This paper will use findings from dental calculus analysis, with important limitations in how it

extrapolates the results, given the limitations in the methodology.

Consumption of Carbohydrates Among Late Pleistocene Hominins

Now, this paper transitions to presenting evidence of carbohydrate consumption using the described methodologies. This section will proceed in two sections. First, it lays out the evidence of carbohydrate consumption directly inferred from dental calculus. Then, it details archaeological evidence of extra-somatic carbohydrate processing. Taken together, this evidence allow the construction of a reasonably comprehensive landscape of carbohydrate consumption and processing, extracting important insights and trends across geography and time period.

Carbohydrate Consumption Inferred from Dental Calculus

Table 1 offers a compilation of some important findings that show direct evidence of carbohydrate consumption. The specific entries of this table, while only a fraction of the available findings, have been chosen for their wide recognition as significant findings in the field of archaeology, combined with their ability to paint a broad picture of consumption patterns across various late Pleistocene hominin populations.

Broad Trends The results presented in Table 1 reveal notable and important trends. Specifically, they highlight a wide variation in the types of carbohydrates consumed, ranging from grass seeds and underground storage organs (USOs) to legumes, seeds, nuts, acorns, and more [9], [11], [12]. This illustrates the reality that consumption patterns were subject to resource availability. However, it also shows that carbohydrates from plant sources were an important component in various hominin populations' diets. The variance shows that these hominins were able to utilize the plant resources in their environments, across various time periods and geographic region.

Another important insight comes from a notable consistency across the findings. Many of the findings identified the presence of grass seeds and USOs in dental calculus, despite extreme temporal and spatial differences between the populations in the studies, [9], [12]. This points to the important role that these specific sources of carbohydrates played in some late Pleistocene hominin diets.

Recall the analysis of dental calculus, and the limitations of the methodology. This indicates an im-

Carbohydrate Consumption Evidence in Dental Calculus					
Date	Location	Species	Finding	Results	Source
120 - 80 kya	Fuyan Cave, Daoxian, South China	Homo Sapien	47 teeth	32 starch granules from acorns, roots, tubers, grass seeds	[9]
49kya	El Sidron Cave, Spain	Neanderthal	2 individuals	Starch granules from mushrooms, pine nuts, and moss	[11]
46 kya	Shanidar Cave, Iraq	Neanderthal	3 teeth	73 Starch granules from grass seeds (wheat, barley, and rye), legumes, underground storage organ. Additionally, there were phytoliths, from the fruits of date palm	[12]
36 kya	Spy Cave, Belgium	Neanderthal	4 teeth	136 starches, from grass seeds and USOs, similar to water lilies	[12]
15 - 13.7 kya	Grotte des Pigeons, Morocco	Homo Sapien	672 teeth	22 starch taxa, from acorns, pine nuts, wild pulses, and oats	[13]

Table 1: Evidence from Dental Calculus

portant contextualization of these results. Namely, these results cannot claim to offer a comprehensive landscape of carbohydrate consumption among hominins in these populations. Instead the dental remains indicate the presence of carbohydrate consumption among the specified populations. However, this allows for the extrapolation of important conclusions. Specifically, the widespread findings of carbohydrate consumption across geography and time period demonstrates that carbohydrates from various sources played a significant role in the diets of some late Pleistocene hominin populations. This role varied by environmental availability, but was notably consistent, in some ways, across geography and time period.

Detailed Insights from Specific Findings Specific findings from the Shanidar Cave site in Iraq offers remarkable insights into not only the consumption, but the processing of carbohydrates. Starch granules in dental remains were found to have been altered in a way consistent with thermal processes, like boiling [12]. Figure 2 displays the findings, picturing both the raw and cooked starches found in the dental remains, compared to modern proxies.

Additionally, the study found starch granules from a variety of plant sources, including grass seeds, akin to wheat, barley, and rye, along with legumes and USOs [12]. Taken together, this evidence shows a sophisticated utilization of plant resources.

Findings from the Spy Cave site in Spain found evidence of starch granules from USOs consistent with water lilies and various grass seeds [12]. The study suggested that these starches appeared to have been deliberately prepared through some thermal means. It interprets the evidence of grass seeds and USOs as evidence of deliberate preparation, given the moder-

Figure 2: Starch grains found in the dental remains from Shanidar III, compared to modern barley starch grains. (A and B) Starch grains from Shanidar sample tooth 4, shown in normal and polarized light. (C) Cooked starch from Shanidar sample tooth 5. (D and E) Starch from current wild barley, shown in normal and polarized light. (F) Starch from boiled modern domesticated barley. Modified from [12].

ate to high levels of preparation that would have been required for consumption - husking the grass seeds and retrieving submerged USOs [12]. Once again, the evidence presents a convincing picture of sophisticated carbohydrate manipulation and consumption, indicating a broad understanding of the integration of plant resources into the survival strategies of late Pleistocene Hominins.

Extra-Somatic Carbohydrate Processing Inferred from Archaeological Findings

This paper will now transition from presenting the direct evidence of carbohydrate consumption to presenting direct evidence of carbohydrate processing. Specifically, it will show findings that indicate two

Extra-Somatic Carbohydrate Processing Evidence					
Date	Location	Species	Finding	Results	Source
250 - 125 kya	Payre, Ardeche, France	Neanderthal	182 minimally handled stone artifacts	Starchy plant processing was identified by the presence of starch grains, with significant quantities of starch from USOs and grass seeds.	[14]
100 kya	Ngalue, Mozambique	Homo Sapien	70 Stone Tools	Starch granules from mostly grass seeds, but also, legumes, nuts.	[15]
65 - 48 kya	Kebara Cave, Mt. Carmel, Isreal	Unknown	Large collection of charred seeds, legumes and other vegetal food remains	Starches included acorns, legumes, and cereals. Seeds of grasses were found, including wild barley grains.	[16]
25 kya	Bilancino, Florence, Italy	Homo Sapien	A grindstone	Starches from more than one kind of plant, with rushes (Typha) and grasses (Gramineae) predominating.	[17]
19 kya	Sea of Galilee, Israel	Homo Sapien	20 charred grains	Mostly charred barley, with some emmer wheat and other grass seeds	[18]

Table 2: Evidence of Extra-Somatic Carbohydrate Processing

predominant methods of dietary carbohydrate processing - cooking and grinding. This is highly relevant to the landscape of carbohydrate consumption among populations of late Pleistocene hominins, given the degree to which processing impacts the nature of the plants consumed.

Broad Trends The results presented in Table 2 reveal notable and important trends. The diversity of geographical regions and time periods where scientists found evidence of carbohydrate processing indicates that processing techniques like cooking and grinding were prevalent.

Grinding, scraping, and pounding plants using stone tools appears to be a widespread practice. Archaeological findings that analyzed stone tool remains imply a widespread application of stone tool processing to grass seeds, USOs, and more [14], [15], [17]. These practices would have significant implications on the consumption patterns of late Pleistocene hominin populations. Grinding enables the consumption of plants that are mostly inedible, in order to extract edible plant components [14], [17].

While cooking is less frequently documented in the archaeological record, the presented evidence shows that thermal processes were applied to plant sources [16], [18]. Recall, also, the evidence from the Shanidar Cave site, which showed evidence of cooked starch granules in dental remains and findings from the Spy Cave site, which inferred that some of the starches found within dental remains showed evidence of

thermal processing [12]. Taken together, this evidence paints a convincing picture of the application of thermal processes in order to alter carbohydrate sources.

These broad trends contribute to the understanding of carbohydrate consumption, given the transformative effect that processing has on plant sources. It yields the conclusion that some populations of late Pleistocene hominins not only consumed, but also actively processed carbohydrates, utilizing thermal and non-thermal means to transform the plants in their diets.

Detailed Insights from Specific Findings Stone artifacts from Ardeche, France highlight important uses for these tools by analyzing wear patterns [14]. Morphological examination of the stone artifacts revealed wear patterns consistent with scraping or cutting motions. The study indicates that this practice could have been applied to the processing of USOs and seeds [14]. These findings underscore the sophisticated techniques that some late Pleistocene hominins used to enhance their nutritional extraction from plant sources.

Findings from Ngalue, Mozambique paint an interesting picture of plant processing. Figure 3 shows the grinding and pounding implements from this site. Researchers identified the presence of altered starch grains adhering to the surfaces of these stone tools. The study notes that the alterations could have a variety of causes, including natural aging, bacterial

degradation, or culinary practices, such as boiling or grinding [15]. While it is inconclusive in determining the cause that resulted in the alterations, it suggests the possibility of advanced culinary practices applied to processing plant foods. It's also possible that several factors led to the alterations, including a combination of thermal and non-thermal processing techniques [15].

Figure 3: Examples of high-starch-bearing grinding and pounding implements from Ngalue cave. Directly from [15].

More definitive findings from Mt. Carmel, Israel provide strong evidence of cooking. Signs of charring on the grass seeds indicate that hominins in this population could have deliberately applied heat in order to transform plants in their diets [16]. While the specific cooking technique is not clear, the evidence indicates that some form of cooking took place.

Insights and Analysis

This paper now transitions to analyzing the presented evidence and drawing insights from the findings. The wealth of data presented above has profound implications to the landscape of carbohydrate consumption among late Pleistocene hominins.

Dietary Importance of Carbohydrates for Late Pleistocene Hominins

Carbohydrates played an important role in the diets of some late Pleistocene hominins. While there are limits in the extent to which dental calculus can infer consumption patterns, the diversity of plant sources from which carbohydrates were consumed - from grass seeds, USOs, legumes, nuts, and more [9], [11], [12] - indicate that various hominin populations consumed plants in their environment. The widespread findings of carbohydrate consumption, across geographic region and time period, indicate that plant consumption was common, and played an important role in augmenting some hominins' diets.

Evidence of processing, including grinding and cooking shows strong evidence of sophisticated practices applied to transform these plant foods [14], [15], [16], [17], [18]. This underscores the range of techniques that hominins used to enhance the edibility of these foods, and enrich their nutritional intake from consuming such foods. The advanced nature of these processing techniques further indicates that plant carbohydrates played an important role in the dietary strategies of some late Pleistocene hominins.

Comparative Analysis of Dietary Fiber in Late Pleistocene and Modern Diets

Despite a reliance on plant carbohydrate sources among some populations of hominins in the late Pleistocene, the landscape of carbohydrate consumption is markedly different than the landscape of carbohydrate consumption among modern humans, primarily in the fiber content that accompanied carbohydrate consumption. While it's true that carbohydrates played an important role in late Pleistocene hominin diets, as they do today [19], the carbohydrate sources they consumed had significantly higher fiber content than common modern carbohydrate sources.

Table 3 compares common sources of carbohydrates that late Pleistocene Hominins consumed, compared to modern sources of carbohydrates. The results are striking. Fiber content in modern carbohydrate sources is significantly lower than the fiber content in any of the sources consumed by late Pleistocene hominins.

This comparison, however, requires nuanced evaluation. This paper has already shown that hominins commonly processed carbohydrates through methods like grinding and cooking. In order to conclude that fiber content differs significantly between the late Pleistocene and modern day, it is crucial to verify that the processing techniques employed by late Pleistocene hominins retained much of the fiber in the plant sources.

Food	Fiber Content (grams of fiber per 100 grams)	Source
Foods consumed by Late Pleistocene Hominins		
Grass Seeds	10.1 - 22.2	[20]
Legumes (Nuts, Beans)	31.0 - 43.4	[20], [21]
Roots and Tubers	23.7 - 39.5	[21]
Foods consumed by modern humans		
White Flour	2.7	[22]
White Rice, cooked	0.3	[23]
Brown Rice, cooked	1.8	[23]
White Potato, cooked	2.1	[23]
Cereal, whole wheat	1.6	[23]

Table 3: Fiber Contents of Various Foods consumed by Late Pleistocene Hominins and modern humans

Consider the practice of cooking, which was commonly employed during hominins in this era. Studies on the effects of cooking reveal that the practice does not substantially reduce the fiber content of various plant sources. While the exact proportion differs by specific food and cooking technique, thermal processing typically does not reduce a plant’s fiber content by more than around 10% [21]. This relatively minimal reduction does not invalidate the claim regarding fiber content, as Table 3 indicates that modern carbohydrate sources contain significantly less fiber than the late Pleistocene sources, even after a 10% reduction.

Other techniques, like grinding, pounding, and scraping transform plant source, often by removing fibrous, inedible exteriors. This type of processing does reduce the fiber levels in various plant sources, but, again, this reduction does not begin to approach the fiber levels of modern carbohydrate sources. While the decrease in fiber content varies drastically based on the specific food and processing technique, the proportional decrease in fiber content typically ranges between 0% and 25% [24]. For example, barley, a common grass seed consumed among late Pleistocene hominins, naturally contains approximately 15.0-24.1 grams of fiber per 100 grams. After processing techniques, which typically includes dulling, the fiber content drops to about 11.0-15.7 grams of fiber per 100 grams [25]. This reduces the fiber content, but it does not nearly approach the fiber content of most modern sources.

Conclusion

This paper has outlined evidence that yields the following main contributions:

- Carbohydrates played a significant dietary role for some late Pleistocene Homo Sapiens and Neanderthals.
- These hominins processed carbohydrates, utilizing practices such as cooking and grinding
- Despite such processing, the fiber content accompanying their dietary carbohydrates remained considerably higher than what is typically observed in modern diets.

The analysis began by outlining the methodology that scientists use to infer diets among late Pleistocene hominins. This section detailed the primary technique that yields direct evidence of plant consumption, analyzing dental calculus. It then proceeded to present evidence of carbohydrate consumption, inferred from dental remains. Subsequently, it presented evidence of various processing techniques, including grinding and cooking. After presenting all of the evidence, it transitioned to analyzing the insights derived from the findings.

Taken together, this painted a detailed picture of carbohydrate consumption among late Pleistocene hominin populations. It also revealed insights that are highly relevant to the modern day.

Modern day health complications, including obesity, diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases are often attributed to diet [26] The analysis in this paper contributes to our understanding of the environmental conditions and dietary landscape in which our ancestors lived. The substantial divergence between modern carbohydrate consumption and late Pleistocene carbohydrate consumption underscores the reality that modern diets may not reflect the dietary landscape in which our species evolved. While modern day health complications are often multifaceted, this dietary divergence is notable and relevant in considering the causes of such conditions.

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